

Propulsion biomechanics during wheelchair turning manoeuvres in young able-bodied men and women

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Abstract The purpose of this study was to characterize push characteristics and force requirements of left (TL) and right (TR) turnings compared with straight-line (SL) propulsion between men and women. Twenty able-bodied subjects (10 men; 10 women, age: 26 ± 5 years, height: 1.68 ± 0.07 m, body mass: 64.2 ± 8.4 kg) received a 12-min familiarization trial of multiple turns around a rectangular course. Subsequently, they performed three tasks in a random order: SL, TR and TL. A Smart^{wheel} was mounted at the right wheel of a standard wheelchair to measure forces and timing parameters of the inner hand during TR or the outer hand during TL. A repeated measure analysis of variance was used to detect the difference across tasks and groups ($P < 0.05$). In the turning manoeuvres, adjustments were made in the approach, turning and depart phase. Speed of TR and TL was lower compared with SL ($P < 0.05$). TR was accomplished by retarding speed, initiated in the approach phase, accompanied by increasing braking force of the inner hand (11.2 times higher compared with SL) and changing push characteristics (higher frequency) of the outer hand during the turning phase. In TL, peak force and most timing parameters were similar to SL, except the approach phase (lower peak force for TL). Differences in speed and peak force requirements were found between genders ($P < 0.05$). It can be concluded that turning manoeuvres require unique execution of force requirements and push characteristics, which needs further study and need to be taken into consideration in the effort to preserve upper limb function. Sex differences in force and push characteristics exist during turning. This is the first study addressing turning biomechanics in wheelchair propulsion.

Keywords Wheelchair propulsion, turning, activities of daily living, mobility

Introduction

Manual wheelchair users often inevitably encounter a variety of daily propulsion activities in various challenging environments such as changing direction while moving forward (Sonnenblum, Sprigle et al, 2012). Sixty three percent of real-life propulsion bouts are dominated by slow and short changes in wheelchair speed and direction (Sonnenblum, Sprigle et al, 2012). Turning along figure eight-shaped course at a maximum speed showed large propulsion force and braking force (Hwang, Lin et al, 2016). Higher peak forces and moments are linked to a high risk of upper limb injury in manual wheelchair users (Boninger, Cooper et al, 1997), so particularly turning movements with their rather high peak forces could be potentially associated with a higher injury risk. The aim of the present study was to compare the timing parameters and force requirements of turns to those indicated in straightforward propulsion and between men and women.

Methods

Participants

Twenty able-bodied adults (10 men; 10 women, age: 26 ± 5 years, height: 1.68 ± 0.07 m, body mass: 64.2 ± 8.4 kg) participated in this study.

Experimental set-up and procedures

Participants received a 12-min familiarization. Subsequently, they performed three tasks: straight-line propulsion (SL); turning 90° to the right (TR) and left (TL). A Smart^{wheel} was mounted at the right wheel. Adjustments were made in the approach, turning, and depart phase compared to SL. Ten trials of each task were collected for processing and analysis.

Statistics

A repeated measure was used to detect the difference across maneuvers and groups. Level of significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

Results

Overall Speed

There was a significant task effect ($p < 0.001$), group effect ($p < 0.01$) and interaction effect ($p < 0.01$). Men was faster than women in SL ($p < 0.05$), see **Table 1**. Participants demonstrated that SL was faster than TR ($p < 0.001$) and TL ($p < 0.001$). TL was also faster than TR ($p = 0.00$).

Force requirement

Comparisons of peak force and negative peak force are presented in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Peak force and negative peak force across three tasks in men and women
*significant men to women pairwise comparison. All differences are $P < 0.05$.

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Table 1. Mean values (\pm SD) and statistical comparisons of timing parameters across the 3 tasks between groups.

Task	Phase	Sex	Speed [m/s] ^{†‡}	Push length [°] [†]	Frequency [pushes/min] [†]	Push time [s] [†]
SL		M	0.98 \pm 0.17 [§]	49.17 \pm 8.88	0.95 \pm 0.13	0.28 \pm 0.03
		W	0.72 \pm 0.14	47.23 \pm 11.41	0.84 \pm 0.19	0.32 \pm 0.07
TR	Approach	M	0.78 \pm 0.11 ^{§¶}	45.05 \pm 11.01	0.97 \pm 0.14	0.35 \pm 0.12 ^{§¶}
		W	0.65 \pm 0.13	45.83 \pm 12.72	0.83 \pm 0.18	0.55 \pm 0.24
	Turn	M	0.45 \pm 0.08 ^{¶#}	36.35 \pm 7.38 ^{¶#}	0.34 \pm 0.08 ^{¶#§}	0.82 \pm 0.25 [#]
		W	0.40 \pm 0.11 [^]	37.03 \pm 10.46	0.32 \pm 0.07 [^]	1.06 \pm 0.28 [^]
	Depart	M	0.44 \pm 0.10 ^{¶#}	31.00 \pm 10.94 ^{¶#}	1.00 \pm 0.21	0.54 \pm 0.22 [¶]
		W	0.41 \pm 0.09 [^]	30.68 \pm 9.56	0.88 \pm 0.18	0.61 \pm 0.20
TL	Approach	M	0.73 \pm 0.11 [¶]	41.55 \pm 7.89	0.96 \pm 0.19	0.38 \pm 0.13
		W	0.64 \pm 0.08	40.32 \pm 10.25	0.97 \pm 0.25	0.44 \pm 0.18
	Turn	M	0.67 \pm 0.08 ^{¶#}	44.60 \pm 8.43	1.00 \pm 0.19	0.40 \pm 0.13
		W	0.64 \pm 0.09 [¶]	43.67 \pm 7.74	0.97 \pm 0.29	0.46 \pm 0.21
	Depart	M	0.69 \pm 0.07 ^{§¶}	46.48 \pm 0.05	1.04 \pm 0.18	0.39 \pm 0.12 [§]
		W	0.59 \pm 0.10	41.40 \pm 13.13	0.89 \pm 0.15	0.52 \pm 0.14

* significant main effect for Task, † significant main effect for Group, ‡ significant interaction between Task x Group, § significant men to women pairwise comparison, ¶ the value is different from SL in men, || the value is different from SL in women, # the value is different from approach phase in men, ^ the value is different from approach phase in women, \$ the value is different from depart phase in men, ¶ the value is different from depart phase in women, SL=straight line, TR=turn to the right, TL=turn to the left, M=men, W=women. All differences are P < 0.05.

Conclusion

Sex differences in force requirements and push characteristics exist during turns. Turning manoeuvres require unique execution of force requirements and push characteristics, which needs further study and need to be taken into consideration in the effort to preserve upper limb function.

References

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